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A Detail Study on Avifaunal Diversity and Distribution in the Wetland: A Case Study in the Tabha Beel, Barpeta District, Assam

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Abstract:

Wetlands are a broad category of aquatic environments that include, among other places, riverine flood plains, backwaters, lagoons, swamps, and marshes. Wetlands are areas that are covered in water, either all the time or only occasionally. Wetlands are essentially different from fully terrestrial ecosystems and strongly dependent on them since they are the meeting point of aquatic and fully terrestrial ecosystems (Black, 1986). In Assam, wetlands known

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locally as “Beels” are significant geomorphic units that play a significant role in the local environment and economics. In the Barpeta district of Assam, there are about ninety-seven beel. Because of its wide distribution, the Tabha beel is one of the biggest. A study was conducted in the beel from October 2019 to May 2020 to evaluate the condition and primary threats to the aquatic avifaunal variety there. The birds are photographed with a high-resolution digital camera, and the birds that are farther away are identified with a binocular. With the assistance of various field guides and the local population, some water birds have been recognized. A total of 40 species of birds belonging to 14 families was recorded. Thirty species total, of which forty are least concerning (90.74%), three are near-threatened (3.16%), one is vulnerable (1.05%), and one is endangered (1.05%). Due to numerous human-caused concerns to the beel’s avifaunal diversity, the number of water birds is steadily declining. Therefore, through this study, it is suggested to declare the wetland as a bird sanctuary to save the birds from extinction.

Keywords: Waterbirds, Anthropogenic threats, endangered species, Barpeta district

1. Introduction:

According to The Ramsar Conventions, Article 1.1, 1971, wetlands are areas of marsh, fen, peatland, other temporary water body containing fresh, brackish, or salty water that is either static or moving, including areas of marine water with a low tide depth of no more than six metres. In addition to being an excellent source of food, wetlands offer a variety of water birds with nesting materials and a suitable environment. Many internationally significant birds have been observed to move to wetlands, where they use them as vital habitats for breeding, growing, resting, and wintering, sometimes for as long as a few months (*Jayson and Methew, 2002*).

According to research, freshwater wetlands are home to 40% of all bird species in the globe (*Kirsten and Brander, 2004*). According to *Kumar et al. (2005)*, there are 310 species of wetland-dependent birds in India’s wetlands. Of these, 113 species of water birds have been identified in Assam, indicating a 38% decline in the avifauna of the region’s wetlands. Habitat heterogeneity affects bird diversity (*MacArthur & MacArthur, 1961*). The composition of bird communities would change if natural flora changed in terms of structure and composition (*Fisher-man et al., 1990; Leito et al., 2006; Acevedo & Aide, 2008*).

It has been noted that a number of concerns, including habitat loss, poaching, deforestation, and climate change, are affecting birds (*Parson, 1935*). These wetlands are vital to the region's ecology and economy. Wetlands are rich in biodiversity and home to a diverse array of plants and animals. Furthermore, they offer a means of subsistence to other local residents. The aim of this research project is to examine wetland avifauna narratives, highlighting their ecological significance. This report also covers the threats these wetlands face and the measures being taken to safeguard them. Assam is home to a variety of wetlands, including riverine flood plains, swamps, and marshes.

These wetlands are found across the state; the Brahmaputra valley is home to the greatest of them. Due to their great biodiversity, wetlands are home to a diverse range of animal and plant species. A significant source of revenue for many of the local communities is the wetlands. Fishing is an important economic activity that supports a vast number of people in these marshes. The wetlands also provide flood management, groundwater recharge, and carbon sequestration as additional environmental services. Wetlands are in danger, despite their significance to the ecological and economy of the state. The primary threats are the loss and degradation of habitat brought on by agriculture, urbanisation, and industrialization.

Pollution is a major danger to these wetlands because untreated sewage and industrial waste are dumped into many of these ecosystems. The Assamese state government has taken a number of actions to preserve the wetlands. They include the establishment of wildlife sanctuaries and national parks in addition to the enforcing of regulations that promote the sustainable use of these wetlands. Community-based conservation projects have also been initiated to involve neighbouring communities in the preservation of these ecosystems. In conclusion, wetlands offer the state a substantial ecological and financial benefit. These wetlands provide vital ecological functions and are home to a diverse range of plants and animals. However, because of the numerous threats they face, these wetlands need to be protected for future generations. A multipronged approach involving the state, neighbouring communities, and other interested parties is necessary for the protection of wetlands. They dwell in a variety of environments, including wide spaces, woods, deserts, high alpine regions, and even the ice zone, where it is difficult for people or other creatures to survive. Birds are valuable models and

bioindicators for researching a wide range of environmental issues, and understanding the significance of local landscapes for avian conservation requires an understanding of the composition of the local bird community (*Kattan and Franco, 2004*).

2. Study Area:

The Tabha Beel is eight km from the town of Sarthebari. The beel is situated between longitudes $91^{\circ} 9' 45''$ E and $91^{\circ} 11' 15''$ E and latitudes $26^{\circ} 21' 15''$ N and $26^{\circ} 22' 15''$ N. The Alpa-Ganga watercourse borders the beel on the north; Nasatra village borders it on the east and north; Belbari and Sigra village borders it on the south; Kurihar Pam and Bamundi village borders it on the west. Roughly 294 hectares are covered by the Tabha beel. The beel typically reaches a depth of three to four metres. The tabha beel is renowned for its extensive biodiversity. The beel is subject to both intake and output circumstances.

During the rainy season, the situation affected up to 500 hectares of water. The beel becomes shallower every day, and most of its area is used for grazing during the winter. Rice farming is a common practice around the beel's perimeter. Approximately 350 families depend on the beel either directly or indirectly. Recent years have seen a major water hyacinth infestation in the beel, which has seriously hindered fish development and productivity and created serious problems for fishing communities.

3. Objectives:

The main objectives of the study are:

- To prepare a checklist of birds of Tabha beel
- To calculate the diversity of the birds recorded in the study area

4. Materials and Methods:

The current investigation was carried out in the Assamese flood plain wetland of Tabha Beel in the Barpeta district. Between October 2019 and May 2020, early morning walks on the approved trail, from 5.30 am to 9.00 am, were used to conduct the periodic survey in and around the wetland. Beel sightings have also been made in the evening, though it's better to see the water birds early in the day.

Using its binoculars, the water fowl was identified. On the other hand, 16MP digital cameras with 20X optical zoom lenses were used to snap the pictures. Various field guides (*Ali and Ripley, 1987; Grewal et al., 2002, Grimmett et al., 2000*) are used to identify waterbirds. After *Manakadan and Pittie (2001)*, the standard common names with scientific names were compiled. They are categorised as Ab (Abundant), Cm (Common), Ln (Lesser in number), Ir (Irregular visitor), Rr (Rare), Rs (Resident), Lm (Local migrant), and Mg (Migratory) based on the availability of water birds. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species was used to compile the IUCN status of every bird (IUCN, 2014).

Fig. 1: Location map of Tabha Beel

5. Results and Discussions:

In all, 30 different bird species (Table 1) from 14 different groups were found in the Tabha beel in the Barpeta region in Assam. There are 26 species classified as Least Concern (LC), 3 as Near-threatened (NT), and 1 as Vulnerable (VU) by the IUCN. 16 bird species were identified as Common (Cm), 6 as Rare (Rr), 5 as Lesser in number (Ln), 2 as Irregular visitors (Ir), and 1 as Abundant (Ab) in and around the wetland based on the observation. Ten resident bird species and eleven migratory bird species lived in the Tabha Beel.

Table 1: Checklist of Avian Fauna of Tabha Beel

Sl. No.	Local Name	Scientific Name	IUCN Status	Status in Puthimari wetland
11	Asian Openbill - Stork	<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	LC	Cm, Lm
8	Black - headed Gull	<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	LC	Ir, Mg
3	Black - winged Stilt	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	LC	Ir, Mg
27	Bronze - winged Jacana	<i>Metopidius indicus</i>	LC	Cm, Rs
28	Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	LC	Cm, Rs
15	Common Coot	<i>Fulica atra</i>	LC	Cm
22	Common Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	LC	Cm
23	Darter	<i>Anhinga melanogaster</i>	NT	Cm
17	Eurasian Wigeon	<i>Anas Penelope</i>	LC	Rr, Mg
16	Ferruginous Pochard	<i>Aythya nyroca</i>	NT	Ln, Mg
19	Gadwall	<i>Anas strepera</i>	LC	Rr, Mg
1	Glossy Ibis	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>	LC	Rr, Mg
7	Grey headed Lapwing	<i>Vanellus cinereus</i>	LC	Ln, Mg
5	Grey Wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	LC	Cm
24	Indian Pond Heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	LC	Cm, Rs
4	Large Pied Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	LC	Cm
12	Lesser Adjutant - Stork	<i>Leptoptilos javanicus</i>	VU	Cm, Rs
26	Lesser Whisling Duck	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i>	LC	Cm, Rs
30	Little Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax niger</i>	LC	Cm, Rs
29	Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollos</i>	LC	Ln, Rs
25	Median Egret	<i>Mesophoyx intermedia</i>	LC	Cm, Rs
9	Nepal House Martin	<i>Delichon nipalensis</i>	LC	Cm
6	Northern Pintail	<i>Anus acuta</i>	LC	Cm, Mg
2	Oriental White Ibis	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i>	NT	Rr
20	Pheasant tailed Jacana	<i>Hydrophasianus chirurgus</i>	LC	Ln
14	Purple Heron	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	LC	Ln, Rs
10	Purple Moorhen	<i>Porphyrio pophyrio</i>	LC	Ab, Rs
13	Red - crested Pochard	<i>Rhodonessa rufina</i>	LC	Rr, Mg
18	Tufted Pochard	<i>Aythya fuligula</i>	LC	Rr, Mg
21	Wire- tailed Swallow	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	LC	Cm

LC = Least Concern, NT = Near threatened, VU = Vulnerable, Ab = Abundant, Cm = Common, Ln = Lesser in Number, Rr = Rare, Rs = Resident, Lm = Local migrant, Mg = Migratory

Fig. 2: The IUCN status of Tabha beel

The Anatidae family had the highest number of birds (7 numbers) in the current study. After that, the following families had the highest number of birds: Podicipedidae, Phalacrocoracidae, Anthingidae, Laridae, Charadriidae, and Recurvirostridae each had one bird species; Ardeidae had four species; Hirundinidae had three species; Rallidae, Ciconiidae, Motacillidae, Jacanidae, and Threskiornithidae each had two species.

Table 2: Family wise occurrence of waterbirds in Tabha beel

Sl. No.	Family	No. of Species
1	Anatidae	7
2	Ardeidae	4
3	Hirundinidae	3
4	Rallidae	2
5	Ciconiidae	2
6	Motacillidae	2
7	Jacanidae	2

8	Threskiornithidae	2
9	Podicipedidae	1
10	Phalacrocoracidae	1
11	Anthingidae	1
12	Lariade	1
13	Charadriidae	1
14	Recurvirostridae	1

Fig. 3: Family wise distribution of water birds of Tabha beel

The preservation of biodiversity has become a pressing issue in recent decades (*Turner et al.*, 1990; *Ehrlich and Wilson*, 1991). The growing threat posed by human disturbances is posing significant challenges for global conservationists seeking to maintain biodiversity. Birds live in almost every type of habitat, and the variety of birds in a particular place is often a good indicator of the area's overall diversity (*Furness and Greenwood*, 1993). Because they are known to react to environmental changes, birds can also be used as bioindicators (*Schwartz and Schwartz*, 1951; *Padoa-Schioppa et al.*, 2006). Scientists around the world are emphasising the need for rapid inventories due to the impracticality of conducting comprehensive inventories of diversity, which require an unachievable amount of time and effort (*Noss*, 1990; *Roberts*, 1991; *Ryti*, 1992; *Anon.*, 1993; *Pearson*,

1994; *Chakravarty and Sridhar, 1995; Roy et al., 2011*). Large-scale bird checklist creation has become highly relevant given the increasing acceptance of short-span study-based biodiversity assessment (*Charavarthy and Sridhar, 1995; Roy et al., 2011*). As per *Basavarajappa (2006)*, the aquatic fauna such as fish, crabs, worms, insect larvae, etc. found in the water bodies serve as their primary source of food, while the native flora such as bushy scrub, scattered horticulture plants, and stray trees in the paddy fields are the most favourable sites for shelter, feeding, and breeding for the majority of water birds.

However, because of the numerous anthropogenic activities occurring in and around the wetland, which have an impact on it both directly and indirectly, the diversity of water birds has been declining daily. Additional dangers include ringing bells at night and killing and catching waterbirds with various tools.

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